

EmpowerUs

Socio-Economic Empowerment
of Coastal Communities

Deliverable 1.1

Gender, Equality and Diversity Plan

Version 1.0

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Executive Summary

This Gender, Equality and Diversity (GED) Plan (Deliverable 1.1) is designed to set out a baseline and a strategy for the EmpowerUs consortia going forward. We are particularly concerned with how a gender and intersectional dimension can be successfully integrated into the research programme: its design, its development process, and its implementation. To ensure a successful engagement with this plan, and these perspectives, the consortium has established a Gender and Diversity Coordinator who will be supported by a Gender and Equity Board.

The GED Plan has two purposes. First, it provides a background to key research on gender, diversity, and intersectional issues in marine and coastal community contexts. It also defines our understanding of gender, diversity, and intersectionality. Further, the report introduces a gender and diversity dimension to key research concepts, such as the “Blue Economy”, the “Users of the Sea” and “Empowerment”. In doing so, it seeks to provide a resource and to promote reflection amongst project partners who will implement the research programme. Second, the plan focuses on key methodologies and methods used in the EmpowerUs project: Transition Coastal Labs; Stakeholder Mapping; Recruitment of Hard-to-Reach Groups; and Interviews, Focus Groups and Workshops. It explores these methods from a gender and diversity perspective and introduces key considerations necessary in their deployment to ensure inclusivity.

We end the report by highlighting some key considerations in the formulation of EmpowerUs GED guidelines. This is done to equip and encourage project partners to take GED issues seriously by putting them at the centre of all project activities.

Key words: intersectionality, users of the sea, social innovation, community transitions, stakeholders, inclusive methodologies.

Contents

Document Information	2
Executive Summary	3
Contents	4
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Situating the Gender, Equality and Diversity Plan in EU strategies and ambitions	5
2 Gender, equality, and diversity research in coastal communities	7
2.1 Blue Economy	9
2.2 “Users of the sea”	11
2.3 Empowerment	11
3 EmpowerUs and Inclusive Methodologies.....	13
3.1 The TCL/lab method	13
3.2 Stakeholder mapping.....	14
3.3 Recruitment of hard-to-reach-groups	16
3.4 Interviews, focus groups and workshops.....	17
4 Conclusion and future directions for EmpowerUs	18
5 References	20

1 Introduction

“EmpowerUs will provide innovative multi-actor platforms to empower coastal communities’ transformation to increase socio-economic resilience, wellbeing and job opportunities for a diverse group of community members (including groups characterised by gender, youth, indigeneity and ethnicity), ensuring nobody is left behind” (Grant Agreement Part B, p. 4).

In this internal report, we address the question as to what ought to be considered, conceptually and methodologically, to ensure that EmpowerUs achieves its objective of being inclusive in its approach to empowerment and coastal community transitions. Co-creation and inclusivity are stated as key approaches throughout the project and in this report we highlight important gender, diversity, and intersectional dimensions to realise such ambitions. Important in this context is that all parts of the project (and all project partners and participants) need to consider and address gender and intersectionality issues in identifying and implementing processes for empowering coastal communities.

This is important as coastal communities themselves are diverse – and any possible problems or solutions to socio-economic and/or environmental issues may be articulated differently across intersectional categories. Therefore, attending to diversity is important not only because it is the right thing to do, but it is also crucial in terms of developing sustainable solutions that work for communities over time. To exemplify this, Nordic countries have experienced depopulation of demographics – in particular women and young people (see Faber et al., 2015; NOU, 2020), which has challenged the long-term sustainability and resilience of rural coastal communities. In addressing such diversity challenges faced by communities, EmpowerUs must ask ‘how can we empower diverse community members and communities to identify and implement transition pathways that lead to job opportunities, livelihoods, and futures that are attractive to diverse social groups?’

This report has two functions. First, it will be a useful resource for project participants in that it synthesises key knowledge on core concepts such as empowerment, Blue Economy, gender, intersectionality and ‘users of the sea’, in addition to raising gender and intersectional considerations in the project’s chosen core methodological approaches. Second, it seeks to encourage important reflections amongst the EmpowerUs team with the aim for team members themselves to put gender, equality, and diversity issues at the centre of all project activities.

The report is structured as follows: first we contextualise the report within wider European Union (EU) gender and diversity strategies and ambitions. We then move on to synthesising key literature on gender, diversity, and equality research in coastal communities – including a discussion of the need to consider these issues when i) thinking through the Blue Economy; ii) defining the users of the sea; and iii) conceptualising empowerment. Following the conceptually focused discussion we move on to discussing specific methodological approaches from the perspective of gender, equality, and diversity, before outlining some guidelines and reflections for the EmpowerUs project moving forward.

1.1 Situating the Gender, Equality and Diversity Plan in EU strategies and ambitions

The European Commission’s proposed 2020-2025 Gender Equality Strategy (European Commission, 2020, p. 19) aims at “achieving a gender equal Europe where gender-based violence, sex

discrimination and structural inequality between women and men are a thing of the past. A Europe where women and men, girls, and boys, in all their diversity, are equal”.

The Commission also states that:

- “[I]ncreasing women’s participation in the labour market has a strong, positive impact on the economy, notably in the context of a shrinking workforce and skills shortages. It also empowers women to shape their own lives, play a role in public life and be economically independent” (European Commission, 2020, p. 7).
- “Empowering women in the labour market also means giving them the possibility to thrive as investors and entrepreneurs” (European Commission, 2020, p. 9).
- “In view of empowering women, a new call dedicated to women in the “blue economy” is planned as part of the next European Maritime and Fisheries Fund for 2021-2027” (European Commission, 2020, p. 17).

Moving beyond gender and acknowledging that women are a heterogeneous group, the EU also consider intersectional dimensions of equality – “the combination of gender with other personal characteristics or identities, and how these intersections contribute to unique experiences of discrimination – as a cross-cutting principle” (European Commission, 2020, p. 2).

The need to address “gender-based violence, inclusiveness issues with intersection social categories (e.g. ethnicity, sexual orientation, disability), perform intersectional research and establish a link with the entrepreneurship and innovation sectors” (European Commission, n.d.) is also expressed as a central Horizon Europe focus, in line with the EmpowerUs project.

There are three main levels at which gender equality is considered in Horizon Europe (European Commission, n.d.):

1. For institutions to have a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in place.
2. For projects to integrate a gender dimension into research and innovation content.
3. Increase the gender balance throughout the programme (50 % women in boards, expert group, evaluation committees and research teams).

Taking the European Union’s objectives of mainstreaming gender throughout research projects seriously, EmpowerUs will integrate gender and diversity perspectives throughout the project. While five out of six WP leaders are women we aim for a gender balance throughout the consortium, including the Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs). In EmpowerUs, we focus on three levels of gender integration in our project. EmpowerUs incorporates a gender analysis throughout the project – within the development of empowerment tools (WP3 and 4), in the TCLs (WP2), as well as in the synthesis and evaluation of inclusive transitions (WP5). To ensure that gender equality takes priority in all aspects of the project, EmpowerUs has appointed a Gender Equality and Diversity (GED) coordinator (RURALIS). The GED Coordinator has the responsibility to ensure EmpowerUs is inclusive, equitable and diverse in its approach. The GED Coordinator’s role is to work at both a Strategic project level and within the project team by liaising with WP leaders and Academic Leads to ensure issues of gender equality and diversity are fully represented, adopted, and implemented across the project at all levels and activities (WP1). To support the work of the GED Coordinator and

to monitor the implementation of a successful gender, intersectional, inclusive, and diverse approach, we have established a Gender and Equity Board (WP1) (see D1.2 for details).

Table 1: Members of the Gender and Equity Board

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The Gender and Equity Board will meet every six months or when issues emerge to work to liaison with all work packages in the project to ensure that gender and equity issues are considered in all project activities. Since there will be diversity amongst regions in EmpowerUs, it is challenging to develop and implement a generalised approach and standard that fits all contexts. Instead, we will seek to provide tailored gender and equity advice, support, and processes of relevance to each region. This will be achieved by implementing the following steps:

- The GED coordinator, supported by the Gender Equity Board, will draw on a Gender (and Equity) Impact Assessment approach which is a toolkit developed by the European Institute for Gender Equality (2016).
- The GED coordinator will work as a resource for all project partners. We encourage partners (WP leaders, TCL academic leads or hosts) to contact us at any stage to discuss gender and equity issues specific to their activities, tasks, and deliverables.
- The GED coordinator will liaise with project partners to develop a gender and equity workshop at key project meetings/workshops.

2 Gender, equality, and diversity research in coastal communities

As a starting point, we must recognise that coastal communities are diverse. In EmpowerUs this diversity is linked not only to the diversity amongst countries included as Transition Coastal Labs (TCL), but diversity also exists within each particular community. In EmpowerUs we aim to open the lid on the ‘community’ by attending to different demographics’ experiences and perspectives on desirable futures and how they may differ. We will be focusing on gender and intersectional issues and this section will lay out some key background knowledge on research on these topics.

Research has revealed multiple gender issues in coastal communities. Such research has primarily focused on the fisheries sector (e.g., Gerrard, 1983; Gustavsson, 2020) but lately work has also explored gender relations in aquaculture industries (Pettersen, 2019). Research has generally however been slow in addressing any gender challenges related to other – emerging – blue sectors (e.g. Svells et al., 2022). There is also some research on tourism that is of relevance to a gender inquiry of the Blue Economy and coastal communities (see Svells et al., 2022).

Frangoudes and Gerrard (2018, p. 118), for example, highlight the gender bias in fisheries research, policy, and industry representation by arguing that the focus on sea-based activities – overlooking their links to coastal communities – and the lack of sex-disaggregated data “*seems to have spread the idea that fisheries are exclusively a male domain*”. Contrary to this common conception, studies highlight the crucial roles women play in the economic, social, and cultural functioning of fisheries and aquaculture (Harper et al., 2020; Pettersen & Alsos, 2007) and importantly women are significant to the sustenance and development of coastal places through their everyday practices of belonging to place (Gustavsson, 2022). Women are also known to be important entrepreneurs in the fishing family context (Freeman & Svells, 2022) – developing, often small, businesses around fish products revolving around such things as processing of fish and shellfish, cooking and education (Gustavsson, 2021a).

In addressing the case of aquaculture, scholars have built on insights gained in research on fisheries. In particular, Pettersen (2007) has explored gender relations in salmon farming in Norway and she identified how women were more likely to work in onshore smolt plants than in the offshore sea pens. Others have found that women are more likely to be involved in seaweed aquaculture than in salmon farming, and it is argued that seaweed farming even can contribute to increased gender equity (McClenachan et al., 2022). The significance of such findings for the EmpowerUs project is that whilst gender structures tend to make women invisible in traditional ocean industries, women are indeed participating in Blue Economy industries – and sometimes more so in new emerging industries. The reasons as to why that is has to date not been sufficiently explored and there is a potential here for EmpowerUs – through a gender inclusive approach – to explore how women too can become empowered in ongoing coastal community transitions and what this then means to the directions and pathways of such transitions and to the sustainability and resilience of these communities over time.

Yet it is important to remember that the gender category of ‘women’ is a heterogenous social group with varying positions related to class, ethnicity and sexuality amongst others. With this in mind, it is crucial to not reproduce power inequities in the interest of a (falsely) unified image of women’s interests and their empowerment. Further, adopting an approach that attends to diversity cannot focus solely on gender. As stated in the Grant Agreement we want to also focus on “groups characterised by gender, youth, indigeneity and ethnicity” (Part B, p. 4). An important concept that allows us to do so is intersectionality.

The concept of intersectionality was first introduced by black feminist scholar Kimberlé Williams Crenshaw (1989). The initial intention of the term was to highlight the multiple – intersecting – layers of oppression that individuals and groups experience. The concept has since been taken up in wider feminist theory and has been used to study the intersections between gender and other identities such as ethnicity, class, sexuality and so forth. Valentine (2007) suggests that intersectionality can be studied through the ‘lived experiences of intersectionality’. This approach to intersectionality makes it: “*possible to move beyond theorizing about the intersection of categories to an understanding of how identifications and disidentifications are simultaneously experiences by subjects in specific spatial and temporal moments through the course of everyday life*” (Valentine, 2007, p. 18). In EmpowerUs we draw on an intersectional approach in exploring diverse coastal community members participation and empowerment.

In taking a gender and intersectional approach in exploring the empowerment of coastal communities in transitioning towards more sustainable futures, we also need to adopt a broader understanding of the ‘economy’ to enable us to include women’s and marginalised groups’ often invisible contributions to communities and to their development. Gibson-Graham’s ‘diverse economies’ perspective is particularly useful to our project as it enables us to explore complicated and often hidden relations, contributions, and work that make up the economy as we know it. Importantly all these contributions make up our wellbeing. Cameron and Gibson-Graham (2022, p.1-2) explain that when the ‘diverse economy’ concept was introduced it presented “a language of economy that was more inclusive of the wide range of practices that make and support livelihoods, create and distribute wealth, marshal and steward resources, make infrastructures and shape futures. [This followed] a need to broaden the scope of who might act to reshape economies and, thus, who was the ‘subject of economy’.” To make this thinking more tangible and to illustrate their point Gibson-Graham (2013) developed the iceberg model which explains how particular diverse economies operates (see Figure 1). In EmpowerUs we will draw on the diverse economies approach to broaden the scope of the economy to also include hidden and unpaid contributions and work which in ocean industries and communities are often done by women, youth, and other marginalised groups.

Figure 1: The Diverse Economies Iceberg Model (Source: Gibson-Graham et al., 2013, p. 11).

2.1 Blue Economy

EmpowerUs engages with ocean developments and how this is associated with coastal community development. During the last few years, there has been a significant increase in research on the ‘Blue Economy’ – also referred to as the maritime economy, ocean economy and blue growth

(Martínez-Vázquez et al., 2021). The Blue Economy discourse is associated with a recent turn in ocean governance where the ocean has become viewed as a ‘new frontier for economic development’ (Bennett et al., 2021). Traditionally, ocean governance focused on a sectorial approach (e.g. focusing on fishing or aquaculture) with the Blue Economy representing a shift towards a spatial management approach – with the aim to grow a sustainable ocean economy by making space for expanding and emerging profitable ocean sectors (such as renewable energy, tourism, shipping, bioprospecting and seafloor mining) (European Commission et al., 2022).

Even if there is much focus on the Blue Economy there is no consensus around a definition of the concept (Garland et al., 2019; Voyer et al., 2018). As a new concept, the Blue Economy has multiple understandings associated with its discourse in national and international institutions and how it is materialised in practice. Voyer et al. (2018), for example, contend that the Blue Economy is seen through many “shades of blue”, with particular disagreements around the importance of environmental and social sustainability within the concept (also see Silver et al., 2015). Further, Garland et al (2019) claim, there are three key gaps in the understanding and application of Blue Economy concepts: There is a need 1) to understand and challenge the power structures that enables social justice; 2) to understand differences in what the Blue Economy is in different contexts and places; and 3) the role of scale (the place, the extent to which decisions are made etc.) must be framed and assessed in relation to the socio-ecological “fluidity” in the marine environment. Taken together, there may simply be no clear understanding of the term Blue Economy and therefore of social issues around it.

What is clear however is that government and policy accounts of the Blue Economy are overwhelmingly positive, with development seen as a solution to a wide range of issues. It promises to “provide food, empower coastal communities, power our cities, transport our people and goods and provide innovative solutions to global challenges” (High Level Panel for A Sustainable Ocean Economy, 2021). However, authors are beginning to highlight the potential hidden challenges and injustices. These include “ocean grabbing” (Bennett et al., 2015), the exclusion of small-scale fisheries (Cohen et al., 2019), environmental degradation, marginalisation of women, human and Indigenous rights abuses, social and cultural impacts, and reduced food-security and wellbeing (Bennett et al., 2021). In the light of this disruption, some have even called for a shift from a Blue Economy to a Blue Justice perspective on ocean governance and development (Too Big To Ignore, 2019).

Important in this context is that there has been a tendency to view the Blue Economy as being placed at sea rather than being associated with onshore communities. St Martin and Hall-Arber (2008, p. 780), for example, suggest that “*mining, shipping, energy development, recreational fisheries, tourism, etc., to the degree they are mapped, are represented as occurring in locations at-sea but those locations and activities are only rarely linked to onshore locations or dependent communities*”. In EmpowerUs however we seek to explore the links between the use of the sea and the onshore local communities who may or may not benefit from the Blue Economy. That is, we go beyond the sea space to also explore how the Blue Economy may impact local coastal communities and its diverse constituencies differently. We want to explore and remain attentive to various configurations of social inclusion and exclusion around who ‘belongs’ (see Gustavsson, 2022) to the Blue Economy – with particular focus on those who often become marginalised in these discussions

(e.g. women, ethnic minorities, migrant workers, youth). This approach is closely associated with how we understand the “Users of the Sea” concept (see Section 2.2 below).

Taken together, authors are clear that there are potentially diverging impacts on different social groups and demographics from the roll out of international, European, and national Blue Economy strategies. EmpowerUs will contribute to nuance these discussions by exploring gender, equality and diversity implications of the Blue Economy in Europe focusing in on each region under study.

2.2 “Users of the sea”

In EmpowerUs we define ‘Users of the Sea’ not only in terms of those who are present at sea daily (e.g. fishers, or offshore workers) but focus on the wider context in which decisions, innovations and change is embedded – that is, coastal communities operating in ocean as well as coastal spaces, where women, men and youth are active agents of continuation and change. In doing so, we importantly attend to the wider context in which the ocean economy and relations to ocean space operates.

To exemplify this, fish may be caught at sea (by fishers who are direct users of the sea), but the caught fish may also be processed and sold locally which produce wider benefits to local communities that sustain them over time. Important in such a value-chain example is that different individuals and social groups tend to be involved in different activities. As discussed above, fishing at sea is often seen as being dominated by men whilst post-harvest (e.g. processing) tend to involve more women (Frangoudes & Gerrard, 2018) as well as migrant worker communities (e.g. Rye, 2018). These industries often involve young people and youth as well, or so called “not-yet realised users” (K. Ounanian, personal communication, November 2022) – if not directly, they at least present potential future work opportunities that can offer them the possibility to live and work in their communities in the future.

By viewing all of these actors as ‘Users of the sea’ we can promote a gender and diversity sensitive perspective on social innovation and empowerment where women and other marginalised groups can be empowered to act for more sustainable, inclusive and just change in their communities.

2.3 Empowerment

EmpowerUs is centred on the notion of “empowerment” of coastal communities through the Transition Coastal Labs that will be implemented in six countries. Yet empowerment is an ambiguous concept that could use a little reflection. Central questions such as ‘who’ are we empowering and in what way are they empowered become central to any discussion of empowerment. Further, what power do stakeholder, groups and individuals have and what is the goal of empowering them? In the Grant Agreement, EmpowerUs uses Avelino’s (2017, p. 512) definition of empowerment:

The process through which actors gain the capacity to mobilize resources and institutions to achieve a goal. This process of ‘gaining capacity’ is unpacked along three dimensions: (1) access to resources and institutions, (2) strategies to mobilize them and (3) the willingness to do so.

Empowerment has also been a central concept in women and gender studies more broadly. The leading gender development scholar Naila Kabeer (1999, p. 435) defines empowerment as “the ability to exercise choice” stressing in particular three dimensions of empowerment: i) resources, ii) agency, and iii) outcome benefits (achievements) which resonates with Avelino’s wider

understanding of the concept. Another useful understanding of empowerment, specifically in thinking through the empowerment of women in primary industries, is Pettersen and Solbakken (1998) who discusses how empowerment can be a strategy of change for women (in their case farm women). They highlight that empowerment is complicated as “people may not be aware of their own interests if the status quo is seen as natural or even divinely ordained” (Pettersen & Solbakken, 1998, p. 320). Citing Kabeer (1994, p. 224), Pettersen and Solbakken (1998, p. 320) write: “Power relations may appear so secure and well-established that both subordinate and dominant groups are unaware of their oppressive implications or incapable of imagining alternative ways of ‘being and doing’”. Nevertheless, they highlight that empowerment must be a bottom-up process rather than a top-down strategy – raising the question whether or not one can actually truly empower someone else. They do however settle on an understanding of empowerment as concerned with the redistribution of power between genders, ethnicities, or classes (amongst other) in its goal and process. There are, Pettersen and Solbakken (1998) concur, three conditions that have to be fulfilled for the empowerment of (farm) women: participation, conscientization and solidarity. Each of these concepts are multi-faceted and needs to be further discussed.

- To begin with, *participation* can be shaped by top-down or bottom-up processes and intentions and the extent to which participation can be empowering depend on how participation is done. While forms of participation which is shaped by top-down agendas may be less empowering, ‘transformative participation’, Pettersen and Solbakken (1998, p. 322) argue, is “both a means to empowerment, and an end in itself” as actors experiences of being involved is itself transformative. They conclude by arguing “the quality of participation depends on who is involved, how and on whose terms” (Pettersen and Solbakken 1998, p. 322).
- Second, *conscientization* highlights the importance of understanding one’s own situation as being embedded in (for example gendered, racialized and classed) structures of power. Pettersen and Solbakken (1998, p. 322) highlight that “[t]ransformative participation implies bringing about understanding of one’s situation”.
- Third, they emphasise the importance of moving from individual to collective action through *solidarity*.

Taken together, “empowerment focuses on transformation/strengthening from the grassroots. The concept of empowerment is derived from power and is closely connected to the realization of human capabilities and potential. Empowerment strategies emphasize conscientization and self-understanding as a basis for change through individual and collective action. In a feminist perspective, empowerment must be understood both as a goal in itself, and as a means towards the emancipation of women and elimination of women’s subordination” (Pettersen & Solbakken, 1998, p. 324).

Yet, Pettersen and Solbakken (1998, p.324) highlight that women are not powerless as they “can have considerable power in households, families and in rural communities, but this does not necessarily lead to structural power in agriculture”. Important to EmpowerUs is the need to view women and other potentially marginalised groups as individuals and groups with agency – yet their agency may be located in less formalised, visible and direct localities. Therefore, we need to keep attentive to how these groups with agency can be empowered – or emancipated – within the context of the project by promoting participation, conscientization and solidarity.

3 EmpowerUs and Inclusive Methodologies

In this part, we will reflect on the core methodologies planned to be used in EmpowerUs. We will in particular discuss these methodologies from a gender, equality, and diversity perspective, including some early reflections of potential emergent challenges and key considerations that needs to be taken in deploying these methodologies.

With the aim of EmpowerUs in mind, we will seek to deploy methodologies that enable wider inclusivity throughout the project. At the end of the project, we will not only have developed a ‘Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies’ (Task 5.3, D.5.2) but we will also have assessed the successes of EmpowerUs’ use of inclusive methodologies, including any challenges encountered and lessons learned when implementing and developing the project (Task 5.4). We will do so by assessing project methods and outcomes as well as interviewing relevant project stakeholders.

Throughout the project, EmpowerUs applies a multi-method and multi-actor approach characterized by participatory methods and co-creation of knowledge. More specifically, we use *Transition Coastal Labs* (TCL), inspired by the living lab method, established in six countries (Ireland, Norway, Bulgaria, Spain, Cyprus, Aaland (Finland)), to examine our project aims and to implement a tailored empowerment intervention. Within the TCL approach we use more specific methodologies and methods, and we will discuss these from a gender and diversity perspective below. Important to note is that there are similarities across these specific methodologies in terms of what is required for them to be gender and diversity inclusive. For example, there is some overlap in gender and diversity considerations needed across stakeholder mapping, interviews, focus groups and workshops (all discussed below). We end each section with a set of recommendations for project participants to consider throughout project implementation.

3.1 The TCL/lab method

“Living labs” are often used to stimulate user-involved and user-driven innovation (Hussain et al., 2019), which echo the goal and approach of EmpowerUs and our TCL labs. There are different understandings and definitions of the living lab method, but some common features are the focus on inviting different collaborators, including citizens and the public, as well as addressing different themes to co-create, validate, and test new services, ideas, markets, and technologies in ‘real-life’ contexts (Zavratnik et al., 2019; Potters et al., 2022; Kvam & Stræte, 2022).

In EmpowerUs we define co-creation as a “collaborative approach to engagement that allows stakeholders to collectively design and build more inclusive and sustainable mechanisms for change” (Grant Agreement Part B, p. 4). The goal is to identify assets, barriers, and opportunities to enhance the socio-economic empowerment of users of the sea and reflect upon, discover, and try out different solutions in cooperation with the coastal labs. As part B in the EmpowerUs Grant Agreement (p. 7) further point out, “the TCLs will be set up to involve multi-actors to co-define the challenges and possible solutions as well as their feasibility, identify together, pilot and test co-developed solutions to coastal challenges”.

As the TCLs include a form of real-life testing (or an intervention), as many definitions of living labs do, the inclusiveness and gender and diversity dimensions need to be taken into consideration in its design and implementation. This means considering who partakes in the Lab, who takes part in the testing and who the intervention is benefiting. Coming back to the concept of empowerment

introduced above, it is important to recognise that empowerment of marginalised groups (women, migrant workers, ethnic groups, youth etc) relies on ‘transformative participation’ (Pettersen & Solbakken, 1998) where conscientization of how individuals and social groups are embedded in wider structures of power as well as collective action through solidarity are key to achieving empowerment. In EmpowerUs we focus on empowerment on two levels: empowerment of the community, as well as empowerment of marginalised individuals and groups within these communities. The TCLs have to keep both these dimensions in mind. Further, it is important to not just have an economic scope but widen the lens to realize wider inclusion of *all* “users of the sea” (see Section 2.2), not just focusing on the ocean, but also on coastal space more broadly.

Recommendations:

- The scope of the TCLs needs to include a socially marginalised group (characterised by for example gender, ethnicity, migration status, age, class, or sexuality).
- Interrelatedly, the TCLs need to consider how marginalised individuals, groups and stakeholders can be empowered within the lab at the same time as it seeks to empower the community more widely.
- The scope of the TCL needs to consider more hidden or invisible activities and contributions that contribute to community sustainability (see the ‘diverse economies’ approach in Section 2 and the iceberg model in Figure 1).

3.2 Stakeholder mapping

Stakeholders can be defined as groups or individuals who have a stake, gets effected by, or have an expectation in a certain case, process or topic. Stakeholder mapping relates therefore to finding and analysing who these stakeholders are, and to map their interest, expectations and power in the project or case that is being studied (Johnson et al., 1993, p. 181-183).

In EmpowerUs we will be mapping the stakeholders in the coastal community TCLs. Marine stakeholders are often defined according to sectorial and economic categories – such as primary uses and users (e.g. fishers, aquaculture, wind power companies), private/public institutions, nature interest groups, recreational users, subsistence users and so on. These are all relevant stakeholder categories to EmpowerUs.

Yet, from a gender perspective, as discussed in Section 2, marine space and its related economic activities has at large been male dominated and women’s roles and contributions have been given little attention (Williams, 2008a; Frangoudes & Gerrard, 2019; Bennet et al., 2021). This has tended to be the case even though women make several important contributions to marine industries and coastal communities. An example of this is in fishing where women are often actively involved in roles such as administration, fixing fishing gear, selling fish, etc., - activities that often take place on land (Kleiber et al., 2015). Women have as such been seen to be what Thorsen et al. (1993) has called ‘the flexible gender’. Thorsen (1993) in particularly focused on farm women but the term perhaps even better describes the role of women in coastal communities as a flexible work force, fitting into all kinds of roles and at short notice. Another example comes out of France where many women are not being paid for this kind of work as they are seen as the “main fisherman’s” wife (Frangoudes & Keromnes, 2008; Gustavsson et al., 2021). We must attend to the gendering of power relations within marine and coastal space, and therefore we need to expand the focus beyond the

sea and include issues that are not always traditionally seen as marine activities (see Gustavsson et al., 2021 for a discussion of fisheries).

Even if much gender literature in marine contexts focus on a binary gender definition (e.g. men and women), it is important to recognise that non-binary gender identities can be relevant in contexts where EmpowerUs operates. Therefore, we need to adapt our methods to be inclusive beyond binary gender identities (i.e. include a non-binary option in when mapping and engaging with stakeholders).

Beyond gender, migrants often stand out as “foreigners” and “outsiders” in rural communities – yet it is important to include them to gain a fuller understanding into the dynamics of changes in rural societies (Rye, 2018). Others have also highlighted that children/youth in many Norwegian coastal communities have been – and still to some extents are – participated in the economically lucrative seasonal job of cutting cod tongues, as this is seen as an important arena for recruitment into the fisheries (Sørensen, 2001). Taken these examples together, it is important to recognise how such unpaid, underpaid, non-economic and/or seasonal/temporary contributions and contributors have a stake in and influence over the future of the community. As such, they are stakeholders. Important to this discussion is that if stakeholder mapping is determined by who is the official/registered “worker” at sea, earning money, has ownership etc. we risk excluding important groups, such as women, youth, or migrant workers. If we are to define stakeholders as people with material interest in the use, development, management or ownership of the area and its assets, we need to operate with a broad definition of material interest, and not just include obvious groups with the risk of excluding marginalised groups. In EmpowerUs we therefore need to move beyond a focus on stakeholder categories as defined by economic and sectoral categories, to also explore the varying experiences of diverse social groups within (and sometimes even considered peripheral to) such categories.

To conclude, stakeholder mapping should not be steered only by registered ownership, salary, and who’s present at sea, but have a wider context-view of the coastal space and community itself. In this way, both men, women, non-binary people, youth (also as future stakeholders) and migrants (amongst others) should be regarded as essential to the future of blue economy and coastal communities. Importantly each TCL coastal community is different and there is a need to closely explore who these specific (often marginalised or hidden) stakeholders may be in each context.

Recommendations:

- In EmpowerUs we are not only interested in stakeholders who are registered owners, paid workers, or present at sea – we are taking a wider perspective in that we are interested in stakeholders operating and living in coastal spaces and in the community. These stakeholders can be providing crucial support, be unpaid, and/or rarely present at sea, but still important to community development and sustainability.
- Use inclusive categorisations when mapping, describing and engaging with individuals and groups. For example, do not assume all participants identify as men or women: include a non-binary option. Further, allow participants the flexibility to describe their own identity under an “Other” option.

3.3 Recruitment of hard-to-reach-groups

Recruitment of participants is central to most of the methods used in EmpowerUs: the TCLs, stakeholder mapping, interviewing, focus groups and workshops. As discussed above, some stakeholders or stakeholder groups can be difficult to reach and to include. Such stakeholders and groups can be women, young people, ethnic or language minorities, the elderly, or people who simply don't think their participation will make a difference or do not feel part of the community or the stakeholder group targeted. Such stakeholders and groups that are hard to recruit may be referred to as 'hard-to-reach-groups' and such groups and people may be difficult to engage, often because they do not feel empowered to do so. In EmpowerUs we therefore need to adopt strategies and approaches to be more successful at recruiting such hard-to-reach groups.

To exemplify the importance of thinking through strategies, approaches, and techniques in attempting to access hard-to-reach groups, we draw on some research done on women in fisheries. In the recruitment phase, Gustavsson (2021b) found it hard to establish contact with women when using the chain-referral or snowball method, even though this method is often used to reach hard-to-reach groups (TenHouten, 2017). Gustavsson (2021b) reflects upon why this might be the case; first, the women in her study did not share a network in the same way as male fishers did. She found it was easier to access male fishers as key informants helped to facilitate access to their friends, colleagues and networks – which was not a possibility when the women who she wanted to access did not necessarily know one another. Second, Gustavsson (2021b) experienced that when male fishers were the primary contact, they could act as gatekeepers in deciding if they wanted to introduce their family members or not. To only use chain-referral or snowball sampling can therefore cause bias and exclude important groups, because it relies on referrals from initial known subjects and the fact that these subjects have a broad social network with others in the target group (Penrod et al., 2003). Such methods can therefore give already empowered groups more power in deciding whose voices are to be heard and not.

For this reason, it can be favourable to use mixed strategies when recruiting underrepresented or often excluded groups in order to not reproduce inequalities in the recruitment process. There exists a range of techniques to recruit hard-to-reach groups, including respondent-driven sampling, indigenous field worker sampling, facility-based sampling, targeted sampling, time-location (space) sampling, conventional cluster sampling, capture re-capture sampling and others (see Shaghghi et al., 2011; Ellard-Gray et al., 2015 for details). The different recruitment techniques should depend on the characteristics of the groups that is hard to reach in a specific community. We encourage EmpowerUs participants to explore novel recruitment methods to facilitate successful engagement and access to a diverse group of community members.

Recommendations:

- Explore mixed recruitment techniques – reflect on their strengths and challenges – in thinking through successful recruitment of a particular group. Be open to having to change your recruitment technique if it does not work.
- Be careful to not give powerful groups the opportunity to control who is recruited.

3.4 Interviews, focus groups and workshops

Interviews, focus groups and workshops are important methods used in EmpowerUs. These are largely qualitative methods. While there are many advantages to using these methods, in this section we will discuss some of the challenges researchers may face when considering gender and diversity dimensions in planning for, designing, and implementing these methods.

There are many influencing forces to consider that might affect who talks, what kind of experiences one shares and not least who feels empowered enough to share their story in the research context. Researchers need to consider issues around gendered (in)visibility as discussed in Section 2 and 3.2 in connection to gendered ownership, salary, and presence, where women are often more likely to be engaged in 'invisible' and unpaid work (Zhao et al., 2013; Salmi & Sonck-Rautio, 2018). Such power relations in everyday life settings can be transferred into inequitable power relations in the interview context, shaping a researcher's access to women's voices and stories. While couple interviews, for example between a male fisher and a female partner, may provide useful insight into couple dynamics as well as partners adding to each other's stories or challenging their perspectives, there is a risk that one partner could dominate the interview and therefore silence the other partner (Morris, 2001; Zarhin, 2018). Similar inequitable dynamics could emerge in group interview contexts as well.

In exemplifying our point, we draw on some insights coming out of research on women in fisheries. While interviewing couples in fishing households together, Williams (2008b) found it difficult to hear and access the women's opinion on the fishing industry. This was also Gustavsson's (2021b) experience, who writes that women tended to be "co-narrators" of the "male narrative", and she argues it was important to have one-on-one interviews with women to access their stories. Gustavsson (2021b, p. 57) argues, "we have to be sensitive to the 'invisible', undervalued, and supportive roles which women often perform in the industry which shape how they narrate their own, their male partners and their families' lives". While this example may be specific to fisheries, and perhaps so to a particular fishery context, there may be important parallels when it comes to accessing the stories of other marginalised groups in coastal community contexts more broadly. EmpowerUs partners and participants need to remain reflexive and attentive to power dynamics in interview contexts – and to adapt their methodologies accordingly.

This is also something to consider while doing focus groups, where the presence of inequitable power relations can influence who speaks and whose stories are being told. Unlike one-to-one interviews, focus groups are characterised by a collective discussion where group members interact with both the researcher and other focus group participants. When doing focus groups, it is often ignored that discussions are shaped by multiple social contexts (Hollander, 2004). While the aim is to gain insight into a particular topic, promote spontaneous discussion and to stimulate dialogue, if not enough attention has been paid to creating and developing an environment where everyone feels empowered, you might get the opposite. This applies not only to different groups of people, such as fishers versus non-fishers, but also within the same group, for example between fishers themselves.

One should therefore strive to achieve an empowered (group) interview, focus group or workshop that enables marginalised and less powerful individuals, social groups, and stakeholders to voice their concerns and set a context that makes people share their experiences and perspectives. This is easier said than done and require effort, skill, and patience of the researcher. There is a rich

literature on different types of techniques that can encourage engagement in interviews and in stakeholder participation. We encourage EmpowerUs partners to explore and engage with such methods and techniques in designing and implementing project activities, in particular when designing workshops. We particularly suggest the use of Durham et al's. (2014) stakeholder engagement handbook where many useful tools are introduced, and these can arguably be suited for particular situations and circumstances within our project. In EmpowerUs Task 5.4 we will explore many of these tools and methods more in-depth.

In all the methods mentioned above, it is important to consider the relationship and dynamic between the researcher(s) and the participants. The researcher is the ultimate source of authority and is the one who influence and promotes participants' participation in the research process (Karnieli-Miller et al., 2009). It is easy to say that one should try to totally minimize power inequalities, but complete neutrality is challenging. Feminist methodology has therefore moved away from striving towards idealised complete power equities in researcher-participant interactions, towards thinking more about one's own position/positionality in relation to the interview participants in order to understand the context in which knowledge is produced (McDowell, 1992). We encourage EmpowerUs partners to consider how their own positionality shape researcher-participant dynamics and associated power relations.

As mentioned in section 2.3 on Empowerment, it is also important to avoid a top-down approach where the researchers take too much control over the discussion, but instead try to take the role as facilitators to ensure inclusion and diversity in the stories that are told.

Recommendations:

- EmpowerUs partners need to be reflexive when using interviews, focus groups or designing workshops – in particular so to make sure the locality, the setting (individual or group dynamic/ private or public setting) enable participants to express themselves.
- We encourage the use of multi-actor, stakeholder engagement tools that are developed to ensure the inclusion of marginalised or less powerful stakeholders in focus groups and workshop contexts.
- Be aware of one's own positionality as a researcher and how this shapes how knowledge is produced in the researcher-participant interaction.
- The researchers should strive towards taking on a facilitator role; ensuring that all stakeholders feel empowered to voice their opinion.

4 Conclusion and future directions for EmpowerUs

EmpowerUs will provide innovative multi-actor platforms to empower coastal communities' transformation to increase socio-economic resilience, wellbeing and job opportunities for a diverse group of community members. This includes groups characterized by gender, youth, indigeneity and ethnicity, ensuring nobody is left behind. This internal document has reflected upon some crucial key challenges that may arise in relation to how to ensure a gender and diversity inclusive approach in the project. For example, research in fisheries found that women have been marginalized and overlooked, even though they are key stakeholders. To ensure inclusion of relevant community

stakeholders in the development of tailored empowerment pathways, we summarize some conceptual Guidelines that all project partners and labs should consider in all parts of the project;

- EmpowerUs uses an Inclusive understanding of Users of the Sea that goes beyond the sea, and registered owners.
- EmpowerUs takes gender and intersectional issues seriously throughout the project.
- EmpowerUs wants to empower those that have traditionally been excluded in addition to empowering the communities more broadly.
- EmpowerUs seeks to identify various economic practices – as well as those who perform them. As such we go beyond simply looking at waged labour and capitalist economic practices. We do so by considering the bottom part of the iceberg – i.e. those (often invisible) activities that underpin the more visible economy. We encourage each TCL to map their own iceberg model diverse economy (see Figure 2). This can for example be done in a workshop organised and facilitated by the GED coordinator.

Figure 2: A template for a diverse economies iceberg model that can be used to map the diverse economy at play in a particular TCL (Source: Gibson-Graham et al., 2014)

In addition to the conceptual guidelines, we summarise the methodological guidelines below:

TCLs

- The scope of the TCLs needs to include a socially marginalised group (characterised by for example gender, ethnicity, migration status, age, class, or sexuality).
- Interrelatedly, the TCLs need to consider how marginalised individuals, groups and stakeholders can be empowered within the lab at the same time as it seeks to empower the community more widely.

- The scope of the TCL needs to consider more hidden or invisible activities and contributions that contribute to community sustainability (see the ‘diverse economies’ approach in Section 2 and the iceberg model in Figure 1).

Stakeholder mapping

- In EmpowerUs we are not only interested in stakeholders who are registered owners, paid workers, or present at sea – we are taking a wider perspective in that we are interested in stakeholders operating and living in coastal spaces and in the community. These stakeholders can be providing crucial support, be unpaid, and/or rarely present at sea, but still important to community development and sustainability.
- Use inclusive categorisations when mapping, describing and engaging with individuals and groups. For example, do not assume all participants identify as men or women: include a non-binary option. Further, allow participants the flexibility to describe their own identity under an “Other” option.

Recruitment of hard-to-reach-groups

- Explore mixed recruitment techniques – reflect on their strengths and challenges – in thinking through successful recruitment of a particular group. Be open to having to change your recruitment technique if it does not work.
- Be careful to not give powerful groups the opportunity to control who is recruited.

Interviews, focus groups and workshops

- EmpowerUs partners need to be reflexive when using interviews, focus groups or designing workshops – in particular so to make sure the locality, the setting (individual or group dynamic/ private or public setting) enable participants to express themselves.
- We encourage the use of multi-actor, stakeholder engagement tools that are developed to ensure the inclusion of marginalised or less powerful stakeholders in focus groups and workshop contexts.
- Be aware of the influence the researcher-role can inhibit and try to take on a facilitator role who ensures that all stakeholders feel empowered to voice their opinion.

In taking the gender, equality and diversity work forward, the approach will be monitored in WP1 by the Gender and Equity Coordinator (Ruralis) supported by the Gender and Equity Board (see Table 1). In WP5 there are also two tasks specifically dedicated towards developing a handbook for inclusive methodologies (T 5.3) and assessing the use of inclusive methodologies (T 5.4) within EmpowerUs. In addition to these specific efforts all WP leads will have a responsibility to implement a gender and intersectional approach throughout their WP to ensure a coherent and robust approach throughout the consortia.

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EmpowerUs

Socio-Economic Empowerment
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